

The Importance of Technology on Secondary School Students' Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State

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Abstract

The research work focused on The Importance of Technology on Secondary Schools Students Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The research work was guided by three (3) research questions and three (3) corresponding research hypotheses. A fifteen (15) item questionnaire titled: The Importance of Technology on Secondary Schools Students Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State (ITSSSQE) was used. The responses were structured in a modified Likert scale to elicit for information from the respondents. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of sixteen secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State which consist of two thousand two hundred and one (2,201) students. The sample size of the study was 220 students representing 10% of the entire population. The simple random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample size. The research instrument was validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation from the Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University. The research instrument had a reliability coefficient of 0.85 which established that the instrument was reliable using the test and retest method with 20 copies of the questionnaire administered to teachers in Delta State twice within an interval of two weeks. The findings of the study revealed that technology is very important in the provision of Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State and as such recommended that schools in Ogbia Local Government Area should be properly equipped with good computers, internet facilities, e-libraries as well as CCTV cameras.

Keywords: Technology, Quality, Education, Computer, Gadget and E-library

Introduction

To remain globally competitive and develop well citizens, our schools should weave 21st century competencies and expertise throughout the learning process. These include the development of critical thinking, complex problem solving, collaboration and adding multimedia communication into the learning and teaching process. According to Desouza (2010) learners

should have the opportunity to develop a sense of urgency in their learning and the belief that they are capable of succeeding in the school. For students to receive quality education, they must have access to top notch technology. Technology will aid the teaching and learning process as it will allow students easy access to unlimited information. Through technology students will be able to learn rapidly, be able innovative and creative as well as share ideas and contents.

According to Pink (2015) a teacher's pedagogy is often a primary driver of how students develop and learn. Teachers who model creativity tend to fluidly enhance support and develop the tendency of their own students. This can be easily achieved through technology. According to Lazenby (2016) to build teaching disposition that take advantage of the availability of new tools for learning and thinking creatively, technology must be inculcated into the learning process. The teaching and learning process will be very difficult without technology but will be very easy the introduction of technology.

According to Robinson (2011) with digital media contribution to globalization and diversification of ideas and content, there has been a rethinking of how we communicate and share ideas, arts, culture and other forms of content. Technology has much to offer in terms of the teaching and learning process as students are seen in the internet searching for data, ideas and new application for content development. According to Henrikson (2016) technology has led to the explosion of new ideas and better ways of teaching. Teachers have been able to get information on how best to improve their teaching through the internet. Students on the other hand can receive lecture through the internet, source for information on how best to go about their assignments. According to Bolick (2013) technology enables teachers to better interact with their students and also develop their classroom practices and repertoire.

Technology allows for the process of e-learning where the students can learn on line. It allows a free of teaching and learning process. The importance of technology was very visible during the Covid 19 period were students despite the pandemic shutting down the entire globe in terms of movement were still able to access quality education through online classes. Teachers were able to come up with on line and offline classes. The teachers informed parents of time for online classes while students were at home. At the scheduled time teachers came online and taught students and even dropped lessons (offline) for students through WhatsApp messages or on their

mails for them to learn at their own convenient time and post questions in areas they are not clear. Also through technology most secondary schools now have e-libraries where students have access to all the information in the world. With a click of their mouse and key board students can have access to any information they want. Technology has created room for even teachers to have access to teaching aids and teaching materials. All they need is their computer set and access to internet facilities and they would have access to all the information they need at their disposal. According to Bolick (2013) teachers can also arrange their students into learning groups. In this situation students will be able to learn through interacting with their tutors and other group members online and offline. The term discussion group will be used. The group will look at and deliberate on issues that are relevant to them. The group could be big or small groups which is usually made of two to six students, medium group which is usually made up of seven to sixteen students and large groups which usually comprise of seventeen or more students. The essence of group learning is for students to learn from their teachers and even their fellow students. According to Erewari (2019) technology can be a powerful tool to re-imagine learning experiences. Historically, a learner's educational opportunities have been limited by the resources and expertise everywhere in the world. For example

With high speed internet access, a student interested have access to all the contents in his or her subject area and even read ahead of the class.

- 1) A school with connectivity but without robust science facilities can offer its students virtual chemistry, biology, anatomy and physics laboratories offering students learning experiences that would have been difficult to access physically.
- 2) Students engage in creative writing, music or media production can publish their work to a broad global audience regardless of where they go to school.
- 3) Technology allows less experience learners to access and participate in

specialized communities of practice graduating to more complex activities and deeper participation as they gain the experience needed to become expert members of the community.

- 4) Technology allows teachers to be properly supervised through gadgets like Close Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras.

The importance of technology on secondary schools students receiving quality education cannot be over emphasized. For instance with the invention of Bayelsa Prime here in Bayelsa State teachers are properly monitored. Their supervising officers will know whether a teacher is doing his or her job properly or not. On the part of the teachers it has their job easier as classroom activities are properly arranged for them thereby making the teaching and learning process very seamless.

Purpose of the study

The major purpose of the study was to determine The Importance of Technology on Secondary Schools Students Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, while the specifics are to:

- 1) Examine the extent of access to good computer and good internet facilities to aid the teaching and learning process enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.
- 2) Find out the extent well equipped and functional e-library enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.
- 3) Determine the extent gadget like CCTV cameras for the supervision of teachers enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

- 1) To what extent does access to good computer and good internet facilities to aid the teaching and learning process enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?
- 2) To what extent does well equipped and functional e-library enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayesa State?
- 3) To what extent does gadget like CCTV cameras for the supervision of teachers enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level

- 1) There is no significant relationship between access to good computer facilities to aid the teaching and learning process and quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between well-equipped and functional e-library and quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.
- 3) There is no significant relationship between gadgets like CCTV cameras and quality education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of sixteen secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State which consist of two thousand two hundred and one (2,201) students. The sample size of the study was 220 students representing 10% of the entire population. The simple random sampling technique was used for selecting the sample size. The research instrument was validated by three experts in measurement and evaluation from the Niger Delta University. The instrument had a reliability coefficient of 0.85 which established that the instrument was reliable using the test and

retest method. The research utilized a fifteen (15) item research instrument titled The Importance of Technology on Secondary School Students Quality Education (TITSSSQE) questionnaire. The instrument was structured on a four-point scale of Strongly Agreed (4), Agreed (3), Disagreed (2) and Strongly Disagreed. The mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the research question, while Chi-square was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results for the study were obtained based on the research questions answered and the

hypotheses tested. The results from the research questions and hypotheses are presented in tables 1, 2 and 3.

Research Question one: To what extent does access to good computer and good internet facilities to aid the teaching and learning enhance quality education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State?

Table 1.1 Mean and standard deviation score of the mean responses on the impact of access to good computer and good internet facilities on improved quality of education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State.

S/ N	ITEM	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	X	SD	DECISI ON
1	Availability of computer enhances quality education delivery to a very large extent	70 (280)	55 (165)	45 (90)	50 (50)	220 585	2.6	1.6	Accepte d
2	Availability of good internet facilities enhances quality education to a very large extent	50 (200)	60 (180)	50 (120)	60 (60)	220 956	2.5	1.3	Accepte d
3	Online classes through internet facilities enhances quality education to a very large extent	75 (300)	40 (120)	45 (90)	60 (60)	220 570	2.6	1.5	Accepte d
4	Online learning group in schools through internet facilities enhances quality education to a very large extent	45 (180)	50 (150)	55 (110)	70 (70)	220 510	2.3	1.0	Rejecte d
5	Availability of internet will give teachers access to better ways of teaching their student which will enhance quality education to very large extent	80 (320)	45 (135)	35 (70)	60 (60)	220 585	2.6	1.6	Accepte d
	Total average mean	64 (284)	50 (150)	46 (96)	60 (60)	220 562	2.5	1.4	

Key: N: 220 Cut off mean = 2.50 SD = 1.4

Table 1.1 above shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses of students under the Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed and Strongly Disagreed using the 4-point rating scale of 2.5 cut off as the mean value. All values less than 2.5 were rejected. The mean value of items 1, 2, 3 and 5 were accepted while that of was rejected. From the

above it was established that access to good internet facilities enhances quality education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State.

Test of Hypotheses 1: There is no significant relationship between access to good computer and good internet facilities and quality education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State.

Table 1.2 chi-square analysis on the impact of access to good computer and internet facilities on Quality Education.

Variables	Number	Mean	SD	DF=(r-1) (-1)	X2=Cal	X2=Crit P=0.05	Decision
Access to computer and internet facilities and Quality Education	220	2.5	1.4	12	21.50	21.03	Rejected

Level of significance = 0.05, DF = 12, SD = 1.4

Table 1.2 shows chi-square analysis which is 21.50 degree of freedom (DF) of 12 at 0.05 significant probability level is 21.03, which gives a chi-square table value of 21.50. Since the chi-square calculated was higher than the chi-square table value of 21.03, the null hypothesis which says that there is no significant relationship between access to good computer and good internet facilities and Quality Education was

rejected and the alternative hypothesis which says that there is a significant relationship between access to good computer and good internet facilities and Quality Education was accepted.

Research Question 2: To what extent does well equipped and functional e-library enhance Quality Education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State.

Table 2.1: Mean and standard deviation scores of the responses on the impact of well-equipped and functional e-library on improved Quality of Education.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D(2)	SA(1)	N	X	SD	Decision
1	A functional e-library with current e-books enhance Quality Education to a very large extent	70 (280)	45 (135)	50 (100)	55 (55)	220 (605)	2.8	1.7	Accepted
2	A comfortable e-library for the purpose reading will boost students confidence and enhance Quality Education to a very large extent	65 (260)	45 (150)	50 (100)	50 (50)	220 (560)	2.6	1.8	Accepted
3	Having a functional e-library with good internet facilities enhances Quality Education to a very large extent	52 (208)	45 (135)	55 (110)	73 (73)	220 (516)	2.4	1.8	Rejected
4	Having e-library with all the modern facilities enhance Quality	60 (240)	45 (135)	50 (100)	65 (65)	220 (540)	2.5	1.8	Accepted

	Education to a very large extent								
5	Having a well- organized e-library with good computers enhance Quality Education to a very large extent	55 (251)	60 (180)	50 (100)	55 (60)	220 (605)	2.7	1.3	Accepted
	Total average mean	60 (251)	49 (147)	49 (147)	45 (224)	224 (444)	2.6	1.7	

Key: N = 220, cut-off mean = 250, SD = 1.7

Table 2.1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses from the respondents on the impact of e-library facilities on secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The 4-point rating scale was used with a cut-off mean of 2.5. All mean less than the cut-off mean was rejected and those equal to or greater than 2.5 were accepted. Items 1, 2, 4 and 5 were accepted, while item 3 was rejected. This shows that good r-library facility enhances Quality Education.

Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Test of hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between well-equipped and functional e-library and Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	DF=(R-1) (C-1)	X2=cal	X2=crit P=0.05	Decision
Well-equipped and functional e-library and Quality Education	420	2.5	1.7	12	39.75	21.03	Rejected

Level of significance = 0.05, DF = 12, SD = 1.7

From the table above, the chi-square calculated at 39.75 is greater than the chi-square table value of 21.03 at 0.05 probabilities significant level of 12 degree of freedom (DF). This shows that the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between well-equipped and functional e-library and Quality Education was rejected. Therefore accepting the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant

relationship between well-equipped and functional e-library and Quality Education.

Research Question 3: To what extent does gadget like Close Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras for the supervision of teachers enhance Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area Bayelsa State.

Table 3.1: Mean and standard deviation scores of the responses on the impact of gadget like Close Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras on improved Quality Education.

S/N	ITEMS	SD	A(3)	D(2)	SD(1)	N	X	SD	Decision
1	Availability of CCTV cameras to monitor teachers punctuality in class enhances Quality Education to a very large extent	70 (280)	60 (180)	50 (100)	40 (40)	220 (580)	2.8	1.4	Accepted
2	Availability of CCTV cameras to monitor teachers regularity in class enhances Quality Education to a very large extent	60 (240)	75 (225)	50 (100)	35 (55)	220 (620)	2.8	1.6	Accepted
3	Availability of CCTV cameras to monitor teachers' classroom management enhances Quality Education to a very large extent.	63 (252)	36 (108)	70 (140)	40 (40)	220 (540)	2.5	1.6	Accepted
4	Availability of CCTV cameras to monitor teachers instructional delivery enhances Quality Education to a very large extent	60 (240)	50 (100)	50 (100)	60 (60)	220 (550)	2.5	1.3	Accepted
5	Availability of CCTV cameras to monitor teachers proper use of instructional materials enhances Quality Education to a very large extent	55 (220)	50 (150)	60 (120)	55 (55)	220 (545)	2.5	1.3	Accepted
	Total average mean	62 (242)	54 (163)	56 (112)	46 (50)	220 (567)	2.6	1.4	

Key: N = 220, cut-off mean = 2.5, SD = 1.4

Table 3.1 shows the mean and standard deviation of scores of the responses from the respondents on the impact of gadgets like CCTV cameras on secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. All items were accepted as each mean is higher than the linkert scale cut-off mean of 2.5. This shows that all mean values less than 2.5 are rejected and those equal to or greater

than 2.5 are accepted. This shows that CCTV camera gadget enhances Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Test of hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between CCTV camera gadget and Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Table 3.2 chi-square analysis on the impact of CCTV camera gadget on Quality Education.

Variable	Number	Mean	SD	df(r-1) (c-1)	X2= cal	X2 Crit P=0.05	Decision
CCTV camera gadget and Quality Education	220	2.6	1.4				Rejected

Level of significant = 0.05, df = 12, SD = 1.4

From the table (3.2) above, the calculated χ^2 of 21.03 at 0.05 probability level at 12 degrees of freedom (df). This shows that the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between CCTV camera gadget and Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State was rejected and the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between CCTV camera gadget and Quality Education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State was accepted. This shows that CCTV camera gadget significantly impact the Quality of Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study reveals a cut-off mean of 2.5 and standard deviation of 1.4 which is on the extent access to good computer and good internet facilities enhances Quality Education and accepted the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between access to good computer and internet facilities enhance Quality Education in Ogbia Local Area of Bayelsa State. This finding corroborates that of Desouza (2010). The study also revealed a cut-off mean of 2.50 and a standard deviation of 1.7 for Research Question two which is on the extent well equipped and functional e-library enhances Quality Education and accepted the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between well-equipped and functional e-library and Quality Education. Therefore establishing that well-equipped and functional e-library enhances quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. This finding is in line with the works of Bolick, C. (2013).

Finally, the study revealed a cut-off mean of 2.5 and standard deviation of 1.4 for Research Question three which is on the extent CCTV camera gadget enhances Quality Education and accepted the alternative hypothesis which states that there is a significant relationship between CCTV camera gadget and Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Therefore, establishing that CCTV camera gadget enhances Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. This finding is in tandem with (Robinon, 2011).

Conclusion

The study concluded that technology is very important in the provision of Quality Education in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State and as such maintained that schools should be properly equipped with technological devices such as good computers, good internet facilities, e-libraries as well as CCTV cameras.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- 1) Government should provide secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State with good computer and internet facilities so as to enhance Quality Education delivery.
- 2) The Government should provide secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area OF Bayelsa State with well-equipped and functional e-library.
- 3) The Government should provide secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State with CCTV cameras so as to enhance Quality Education delivery.

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